

LOCKDOWN IN A RECESSED ECONOMY: RETHINKING A NEW APPROACH TO PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract:

This study focused on the lockdown in the second and third quarters of 2020 resulting to negative Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate of -6.10% and -3.62% respectively and consequently causing Nigeria's economy to fall into recession with its escalating impact on rising inflation and unemployment rates, youth restiveness, leadership distrust and security challenges in the pandemic (covid19) era. The objectives of the study are to examine within the framework of the impact factors, the strength or weakness of Nigeria's state capability and public sector response to emergencies and/or uncertainties. The researchers utilized discourse approach to analyze class theory, hierarch of needs theory and frustration-aggression theory in explaining governance crisis and the trends captured in the lockdown. The Researchers applied mixed methods for the study of governance in the lockdown. The study concluded that there was governance crisis in Nigeria during the lockdown and state institutions were unable to perform minimal functions as a result of state capture by predatory governing elite class. This indicated that the state capacity was weak to deal with uncertainty like the covid19. The paper argues for a social justice and equality ethical leading approach to public administration and governance to drive integral development in Nigeria and the reforming of political, economic, social and bureaucratic institutions to drive citizens-state relations.

Keywords: Crisis management, Integral development, Lockdown, Recessed economy and State capability.

Introduction

The covid19 with its precautionary measure of flattening the curve of infections have among other protocols required social distancing among persons and isolation of infected persons until the virus is satisfactorily eliminated from their biological system (at individual and community levels). This scenario is metaphorical of Nigeria's governance and administrative system. The Nigeria state is essentially suspended or actually isolated from the people it intends to govern. There is evidence of social distance between the state (or the governing class) and the people (identified as the governed). The social contract binding the state represented by the governing and the governed class have collapsed.

The global covid19 pandemic which started in Wuham China in December 2019 was identified and confirmed in Nigeria with an index case on February 27th 2020 and in March 28th 2020, the government initiated schools and other places with public exposure of above 50 persons to be closed nationwide. Between April and October 2020, the federal government of Nigeria order a lockdown nationwide with exception of essential services, like health, security and food sectors operating under strict surveillance (Aminub, Kolob, Akinyeleb, Ogundairob & Danjibob 2020).

While these measures were precautionary from allowing the exponential growth of the covid19 to escalate into an uncontrollable rate that is unmanageable; the trend of activities and events that played out, exposed the capability of the Nigerian state to be lagging in response (rather than leading with proactive action).

The lockdown of the country between April 2020 and October 2020, essentially criminalized movement of persons and engagement in any social and economic activities in physical contacts and form (since mobile courts were created to immediately try violators). Proactive measures were not put in place to address the welfare needs of vulnerable persons the government imposed lockdown would affect. People are social animals with biological and surviving needs that must be met. Without economic activities and social interactions, organization and society will manifest relapse. This induced recession in the 2nd and 3rd quarters of 2020 with negative Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate of -6.10% and -3.62% respectively for the period (NBS 2020).

Some of the impact factors induced by the recession are escalating inflation rate (cause by low production), increase unemployment rate, youth restiveness, leadership distrust and security challenges. These impact factors are effects and readily point to the character and weak capacity of the Nigerian state in attending to crisis or emergency situations.

It is these impact factors that the Researchers seeks to analyze using theoretical lens and measure of statistical data to evaluate government capacity in containing the condition of the pandemic and provide a leading approach to good governance through an efficient public administration.

Material and method

The study adopted mixed method, a complementary of qualitative and quantitative methods to deal sufficiently with multifaceted research problems; Creswell (2009). The Researchers explored

discourse approach (qualitative approach) to governance and public administration using supportive empirical evidence with statistical value (quantitative approach) to analyze the lagging governance approach in the lockdown period and the consequences of the impact factors on Nigerians and the economy.

Theoretical discourse.

Discourse analysis refers a particular way of talking about and understanding the world with reference to the philosophical, theoretical and methodological or specific techniques guidelines for how to approach a research domain (Angermuller, Maingueneau & Wodak 2014; Jørgensen & Phillips 2002). Discourse analysis as used in this work is captured under the framework of Governance with multi-perspectival elements of class analysis, hierarchy of needs and frustration-aggression theory.

The study and practice of public administration have direct consequence for governance and development in Nigeria. Public Administration was separated from political science as a distinctive discipline because administration was not getting the required attention under political science. As a specialize discipline, public administration is deigned to implement government policies in the public sector, not making them. Woodrow Wilson's article on the study of public administration in 1887, called for the separation of politics from administration with the statement that political questions are not administrative questions. They are related but distinct and calls for different concern and orientations. Uwizeyimana and Maphunye (2014)

Uwizeyimana and Maphunye (2014) noted that from the Woodrow Wilson thesis on politics-administration dichotomy in 1887, three phase of theory development have spanned the study and practice of public administration. The three era of theory development in public administration are the traditional public administration theory with primary focus on politics-administration dichotomy (1880s-1970s); the New Public Management (NPM) theory with primary focus on managerialism and privatization in public sector (1970s-1980s); and Governance theory with primary focus on improving and strengthening institutions (administrative, civil service, parliament oversights, judicial reforms, citizen and civil society participation in decision making and accountability in state affairs (1990s-date).

The focus of this paper is not to discuss the theory development of public administration in detail but to direct our attention on governance theory exploring the institution of state capability as the parameter of analyzing the current theme and era of public administration theory. Establishing the desirability of focus on measuring the position of Nigeria's governance index will be an objective place to start.

Governance is a fuzzy concept. Previous scholars before the 1989 (collapse of the communist bloc) have equated the term or used it interchangeable with government or affairs relating to the autonomous state. An autonomous state is an enclosed state that restrict decision making to only government agencies or institutional mechanism (dominated by the governing elites). Beyond the 1990s, the state is no longer autonomous, it is currently fragmented, disarticulated and largely contested. The fragmentation of the state means government officials and the bureaucracy alone, no longer have the space to determine state policies.

Recent studies have associated the concept of governance to the surge of globalization and democratization of institutions dealing with government and the state. From this perspective, the numerous definitions centered around a multidisciplinary approach that focus on governance as issues relating to (participatory) decision making by collective sets of actors and managing or organizing their diverse interests as a network of relationship, resources and capacity designed for mobilizing and actualizing development goals (Chhotray & Stoker 2016; Ansell & Gash 2014; Peters 2011)

The International Bureau of Education, UNESCO (2021), define governance as structures and processes that are designed to ensure accountability, transparency, responsibility, rule of law, stability, equity and inclusiveness, broad based participation and values through which public affairs are managed. It is power relationship among decision makers.

The Worldwide Governance Index measures governance quality (weak or strong) through a set of six indicators showing broadly diversify institutions (beyond political and bureaucratic institutions) of the state that includes the judiciary, media, citizen, private sector and civil society organizations. The latest report of the Worldwide Governance Indicators for 2019 (released in September 20220) compiled by Daniel Kaufmann and Aart Kraay ranked Nigeria on 144th among 200 countries and territories on six dimensions of governance: (1) voice and accountability, (2) political stability and absence of violence, (3) government effectiveness, (4) regulatory quality, (5) rule of law, and (6) control of corruption. (WGI 2020).

Table 1

	Estimate score	
Nigeria Rank 144	Range from 2.5 strong to -2.5 weak	Percentile 0 (lowest) and (100 highest)
Voice and accountability estimate	-0.41	34.98
Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism	-1.93	5.24

Government effectiveness	-1.09	13.46
Regulatory quality	-0.86	17.79
Rule of law	-0.9	18.75
Control of corruption-	-1.9	12.98

Source: Author, based on Worldwide Governance Indicator database for 2019.

Figure 1.

Source: Author, based on Worldwide Governance Indicator database for 2019.

The Worldwide Governance for 2019 ranked Nigeria 144 with a negative score ratings of -0.49 for *Voice and accountability* (indicating that citizen’s ability to elect public or political leaders, monitor and express their opinion of public policies is limited or weak: score at 34.98/100); -1.93 for *Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism* (indicating there is high resistance against government by violent groups with preference to take over government through force: score at 5.24/100); -1.09 for *Government effectiveness* (indicating that there is dominance of politics against public administration or public bureaucracies, there is lack of commitment towards public policy and their outcomes: score at 13.46/100); -0.86 for *Regulatory quality* (government ability to provide and promote effective regulatory policies that will enhance private sector development is weak: score at 17.79/100); -0.9 for *Rule of law* (political and administrative officials and their

agents lack respect and violate constitutional provisions and court judgements: score at 18.75/100) and -1.9 for *Control of corruption* (indicating high possibility that public official will capture public resources for private gain: score at 12.98/100).

The conclusion derived from the WGI data indicated that the indicators are positively correlated and self-explanatory. All six indicators examined were negative and express a trend that the quality of governance in Nigeria for 2019 is weak. The latest rating of WGI for 2019 is been utilized to measure the Nigerian state capability for the lockdown.

Weak voice and accountability has direct implication for political instability and occurrence of violence/terrorism, government ineffectiveness, weak regulatory quality, violation of rule of law and weak control of corruption. These indicators are complementary and reinforces each other. Summarily, these indicators describe and explain the nature and character of the Nigerian state failure and its lagging approach to governance and uncertainty. This affirmed the position of Okotoni (2017) that Nigeria's development trajectory is implicated in governance crisis.

To attend to the impact factor of the lockdown as a consequence of the derived nature of the Nigerian State and the weak quality of governance, the Researchers utilized class theory, hierarchy of needs theory and frustration-aggression theory as theoretical framework in explaining the trends captured in the lockdown.

Class theory.

As captured by Mosca, Pareto and Michels, all society (inclusive of state) are stratified into two broad classes. Class is the division of persons into groups to represent their location and interest in the ordering of things in society or state. For governance discourse, the two broad classifications are the ruling or governing class (governing elite) and the non-governing class (masses). The governing class comprise of organized minority that possess control of state power and resources. They use their hold on power to manipulate and control the masses' class (disorganized majority) by deploying force and fraud. The self-enlightened interest of the governing class is to primitively appropriate and enlarge their power base and wealth, while the proletarian masses are exploited and deprived of basic necessities (Hartmann 2007).

Power and wealth are consequential to the elite survival and the state is the means to possess both. Marxist conceptualization of class analysis expressed the vivid reality of exploitation and deprivation of the proletarian mass class by the governing elite class to a tendency of a derived consciousness of been oppressed. This knowledge of the consciousness of been oppressed ignite class struggle between the two classes, for the governing elite class the struggle is to retain power and wealth while for the oppressed class, the goal of the struggle is to wither the state. Marx maintained that the state is an instrument of oppression and exist as a weapon to perpetuate the prevailing order in the favour of the governing elite. Convincingly, Marx predicted as the intolerable conditions of the oppressed class is aggravated, the consciousness and quest for revolution will be necessarily directed to the dismantling or withering of the state.

The nature of the Nigerian elite towards political, economic and social institutions of the state is predatory and this typically is manifested in the economic realities citizen are faced with

consequence of the impact factors mentioned above (this is not to state that the list is exhaustive). A look at the economic performance and indicator will reveal governance crisis in the economy.

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS 2020) Q2 & 3 2020 report indicated that nominal GDP (Q2 2020) stood at N34.02 trillion while real GDP (Q2 2020) was N15.89 trillion; a differential of N18.13 trillion with a negative growth rate of -6.10%. Also nominal GDP of N39.09 trillion and real GDP of N17.82 trillion for Q3 2020 with a differential of N 21.27 trillion and negative growth rate for -3.62%. the differentials of N39.4 trillion was accounted for the rate of inflation suffered in both Q2 and Q3.

The NBS report also indicated that sectoral contribution to the economy as share of GDP for 2020 for Q2 were Agriculture (24.65%), Industries 21.87% and Services (53.49%) with subsector of industries, Oil contributing (8.93%) and Non –oil (91.07%). Also, marginal variations occurred for Q3 with slight decrease in Agriculture (21.96%), and slight increases in Industries 23.65% and Services (54.39%) with subsector of industries, Oil contributing (8.73%) and Non –oil (91.27%).

The Central Bank of Nigerian (CBN) Q4 2020 Economic report indicated that inflation rate for the Q2 and Q3 were 12.43% and 13.25% respectively. Among major country's sampled in the report, it is only Nigeria that had double digit inflation for the period, the next to it was India with an inflation rate of 5.2% and 5.53% for the same period. The least country with inflation rate was Italy with (negative) -0.13% and -0.48% for Q2 and 3 respectively.

NBS Q2 2020 report and Price Waterhouse Cooper economic alert for Q3 labour force (ages 15 - 64, those willing and able to work) was estimated to be 80,291,893 (29.1% are youth between 25-34 amounting to 23,328,460 persons). From this figure, 27.1% representing 21,764,617 persons unemployed in Q2 with estimation of 28% for Q3 (PWC). Unemployment/underemployment rate are 55.7%. and 56.7% respectively for Q2 and Q3.

Nigeria's misery index resorting from a high double digit inflation rate of 13.23% in Q3 plus unemployment rate of 28% $(13.23 + 28) = 41.23\%$. This signified that 41.23% of labour force of 80,291,893 are miserable $(41.23/100 \times 80291893 = 33,104,347.48)$. A significant of 33,104,347 persons in the labour force were miserable during the Q3, of which the youth proportion of this figure ranged from between 25-34 years $(29.1/100 \times 331,043,47 = 9,633,364.97)$. This leaves us with 9,633,365 youths in the labour force were miserable in the Q3. If we add underemployment rate to this figure, the number will rise higher than four times this figure.

The social consequence of the misery index is that higher misery index tends to be associated with rate of dissatisfied persons which by implication have distrust for government and leadership (governance), have high incentive to commit crime as means of survival (security risk as observed in robbery, kidnapping and insurgency) increased during the Q3 period. This means that the direction of the misery index can dictate the rate of crime expected in a given country; the higher the misery index, the higher the rate of social disorder, increase of ungoverned space and other form of insecurity and revolutionary tendency against the state. Munir, Asghar & Rehman (2017) and Wang, Shah, Ali, Abbas & Ullah (2019) linked the incident of misery index to the escalation of crime in various countries. Husain (2018) noted weak social and economic indicator can create ungoverned space for a country.

Based on class analysis, a predatory governing elite class enhances a conditional state capture that weakens state institutions to be extractive (preventing majority of citizens to participate in governance and decision making process) causing impact factors with voracious effects in the form of low economic productivity that engage low productive capacity, low human resources utilization/rising unemployment/underemployment and leading to rising inflation and leadership distrust (Ifaka 2016, Acemoglu and Robinson 2012; Fukuyama 2004, 2006, 2014).

Hierarchy of needs theory

Maslow (1943) hierarchy of needs theory posited that man's needs are arranged in order of preference. The physiological needs dealing with man's surviving needs, which requires responding to biological necessity. They are air, food, water, clothing, shelter and sex. Progressively man requires to attain safety needs (to be secure, emotional, financial and environment protection, including job security), other needs are social, esteem and self-actualization needs. These needs are interrelated and significantly impacted on human behaviour and motivation.

The above condition further stimulates a deniability syndrome that once citizens are disempowered and lacks the opportunity and propensity to access or afford the basic needs (food, shelter, clear water, air and sex) of life required for survival, they lack motivation to act in the interest of organizational. When people are unable to meet these basic needs or denied the opportunity to do so, they become frustrated and exhibit aggressive behaviour and actions.

Frustration and aggression theory

Breuer and Elton (2017) expressed that aggressive behaviour is induced or produced by frustration. What this implies is that frustration is a causative factor that produces aggression in human behaviour. Humans are goal oriented and become frustrated when the outcome of their goals are hindered by a preventable cause. They direct their aggression (anger) to the source of the medium that is preventing or denying the materialization of the goal. Frustration and aggression is intense when it is relative to social context, in the sense that inequality or injustice is responsible for deprivation of the outcome.

Apply the discourse framework on governance, it is indicative that weak governance or governance crisis environment is created by the predatory elite class to capture state resources and alienate the mass of individuals or exclude them from the benefits of the common-pool resource, painfully referred to as the tragedy of the common (Ostrom 2015).

Inequality and injustice is a source of frustration that can ignite social aggression or revolution; although the lockdown from the flattening of the covid19 pandemic was inevitable, the EndSARS protest was a response to the poor management of state-society relationship during the April-October 2020 timeline of the lockdown. It depicted a governance crisis that typified leadership distrust by young Nigerians over their welfare and security.

The EndSARS protest which began in October 8th 2020 by young Nigerians over police brutality and stretched towards the end of October, later added request for good governance as a cardinal point of the agitation. The protest was an exhibition of frustration and aggression towards the

Nigerian State. The protest also revealed the predatory nature of the governing elites by exposing the various states government across the country, withholding palliatives in warehouses (food items) met for distribution to vulnerable persons during the lockdown period. The discovery of the hidden palliatives raised the level of anger among young unemployment persons who were deprived by the state and its governing elite to exhibit anarchical tendency against the state and its institutions (especially the police).

Conclusion and Finding

The goal of governance and public administration is to implement policies towards service delivery to citizens. Contemporary studies and practice of the field have shown that the academia and practitioners are more involved in the use of methods rather than creating value directed at substance towards service delivery.

The lockdown policy with its manifest and latent consequences, points to the reality that policy makers (governing elites) were not particular about service delivery. The study evaluated the lockdown policy in the covid19 era and was able to show and identify that there was governance crisis in Nigeria. The Nigerian state was unable to perform the minimal function of a state (state capacity) to make and enforce its own laws during the pandemic period and lockdown; it was also not able to hold claim to its sovereignty and territory, protect lives and properties, promote law and order. The Nigerian state was unable to provide macroeconomic management policies that protect the poor from the rich and the strong from the weak. From the lagging approach to governance, a predatory class organized the affairs of the state for its own interest, excluded the majority of citizens and generated a governance crisis that reflected increasing ungoverned spaces with escalating inflation, increasing unemployment, youth restiveness, leadership distrust and security challenges in the pandemic (covid19) era.

Recommendation (what need to be done)

1. There is the need to approach governance and public administration from a higher value orientation. With the governance approach, the problem of weak institution and exclusion still prevail; this has generated crisis of development and call for disintegration of the Nigerian State. The study and practice of public administration must be value base; it values must be center around not just mere human rights and dignity, but more broadly a social justice and equality model of delivery service delivery for all.

An ethical approach to governance and public administration is a possible outcome with great potentials. China grew out of communism and exclusion and became dominant in global capitalist economy by embracing the Confucian ethics. The Confucian ethics focus on strengthening human relationship and promoting a sense of responsibility to one another. Confucianism core moral values are discipline, education and competence, loyalty, benevolence and humanness, excellence and reciprocity or mutuality. The Confucian ethics are attributes that citizens need to possess and how they respond to the state. Citizens are expected to be discipline or have self-control towards governance and public administration. Demonstrate education and competence in handling public affairs and the state should place the best suited person for the job to handle with competence.

Citizens should be loyal to the state than to put their selfish or ethnic interest before the state objective; citizen should approach the state with benevolence or act of kindness as the state become stronger with a sense of patriotism from citizens. The state and citizen exist for each other, there should be mutuality of purpose driven by the need to provide excellence performance in transactions between the state and the citizen. Shug and Wong (2004).

2. With enlightened citizenry, government and the state cannot afford to treat citizen without respect. Citizens are demanding for transparent and accountable government. Citizens must be included in policy making and execution of state policy and processes. This will require joint partnership or integral approach to governance. All hands must be on deck to drive governance and public administration on national building.
3. Governance and public administration in modern state must be driven by justice and equity. citizen's rights must be respected and protected. Governance must be effectively directed at public service rather than towards the interest of elites. Public administration should serve the interest of all and not only those in government.
4. Reforming political, economic, social and bureaucratic institutions is necessary to drive citizens state relations. These institutions must be reform to respond to the needs of citizens as the owner of the state sovereignty and that state intuitions are created to promote and protect the interest of the citizenry.

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